

Radar Backscatter Modeling of 3D Vegetation Structure

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Abstract — Our current 3D radar backscatter model treats vegetation layers or tree crowns as homogeneous volumes consisting of various scatterers. The volume scattering and attenuation properties of the vegetation layers used in radiative transfer models were calculated by averaging the Stokes matrix (incoherent summation) or the scattering matrix (coherent summation) from these scatterers. This averaging process, by integration over the size and orientation distributions of the scatterers, eliminates the discrete nature of the vegetation structure and creates a continuous medium description of vegetation structure. Certain scattering properties based on the discrete nature and relative position of scatterers, for example, the corner reflectors formed by branches, have been lost in the model. Trees simulated from a tree growth model were used to investigate the effect of crown discrete structure on radar backscattering. This paper presents preliminary results from modifying models for this purposes.

INTRODUCTION

Radar return from vegetation structure is determined by water content and vegetation geometric structure. For example, the

Figure 1. Backscattering from a dielectric cylinder (length 75cm, diameter 4 cm). Radar incidence angle is 45°.

backscattering from a branch (modeled as a dielectric

cylinder) is a function of its orientation as well as other parameters. Only with normal incidence, is there significant direct backscattering from a long cylinder (Fig. 1). Another type of scattering within the tree crown, which needs to be considered, is the specular scattering from long branches. Fig. 2 shows the specular scattering pattern of a cylinder. The peak specular scattering is much stronger than the backscattering. In this case multiple scattering is important. The purpose of this study is to modify our 3D radar backscatter model [1] to investigate the significance of these scattering mechanisms.

Figure 2. Scattering pattern in specular direction from the same cylinder as in Fig.1. The cylinder is in vertical position.

MODELING

The tree growth model developed by Dr. Leersnijder [2] was used to generate two trees: 1) a small 10-year old spruce tree, and 2) a 20-year old pine tree (Fig. 3). The attenuation and direct backscattering from each tree crown were calculated using a method similar to that described by Lin and Sarabandi [3]. The crown attenuation was assumed to be constant horizontally, but a function of tree height. The backscattering from each scatterers were added coherently. If the bistatic scattering width for oblique incidence on an infinitely long cylinder is known, then for a long cylinder, according to the assumptions suggested by Van de Hust [4] and used by Ruck et al [5], there is a zone where the scattered

Figure 3. Simulated trees: 1) small one is a 10-year old spruce tree with 3957 branches, and 2) larger one is a 20-year old pine tree with 6887 branches.

field is diverging as two-dimensional scattering. This zone lies between the radial bounds $a^2/\lambda < r < h^2/\lambda$. The a and h are the radius and the half length of the cylinder. Then the approximation can be made that the scattered field in this region is (i) zero for $|z| > h$, and (ii) equal to that from an infinitely long cylinder for $|z| < h$. (See Fig. 4-47, p. 303 of [5]). If there is another cylinder within this zone, forming a right angle with this cylinder, and if this structure is facing the radar and in the principal incidence plane, backscattering due to double-bounce will occur. In order to simplify the calculation, the illumination of one cylinder by the scattering from another cylinder was assumed to be uniform and equal to those at the center of the cylinder.

Only the radar cross section of a whole tree with a fully absorbing background was calculated. The radar look angle used was 45° for azimuth angles from 0° to 360° with an interval of 10° .

RESULTS

It was found that the contribution from double-bounce scattering is not significant, because very few cylinders form

the ideal structure. Figure 4a is the radar cross section of the spruce. The double-bounce term is in the order of 10^{-4} m^2 and was ignored. The same is true for the pine tree (Fig. 5a). In order to see how significant the backscattering from those branches with normal incidence, we calculated the backscattering from these branches only and plotted the results in Figures 4b and 5b. It can be seen that this is also not very important.

The results from these simulations contradict our intuition that the double-bounce structure and branches with normal incidence would play important roles in tree crown backscattering. This is probably due to the idealized geometry we used for simulating tree branches, that is straight and smooth dielectric cylinders. This needs to be further investigated.

REFERENCES

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Figure 4. a) Backscattering from a spruce tree, b) Backscattering from branches with normal incidence.

Figure 5. a) Backscattering from a pine tree, b) Backscattering from branches with normal incidence.